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Evaluation Framework of Sustainability Reports

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1. Introduction

Sustainability is now an essential aspect for organisations. Companies' clear commitment to the well-being of their employees, environmental protection, and climate change are examples of actions expected by clients and investors. Many companies are incorporating these and other sustainability themes into their businesses, and the sustainability report represents the main instrument to communicate this commitment. Currently, there are some guidelines on how to develop a sustainability report, but no formal agreement on its content. What is known is that the development of a sustainability report should be an exercise that allows reflection on the organisation's impact on society. It is also an opportunity to define ambitious targets and demonstrate how the performance has improved through indicators. A sustainability report can reveal the level of integration of social, environmental and governance aspects into the company strategy.

This framework sought to evaluate how companies communicate on non-financial themes; therefore, the focus of the analysis is not on assessing a company's sustainability performance, but rather, on determining whether the report is transparent, clear and effectively communicates the company's strategy to all stakeholders.

2. Methodology

The evaluation framework for sustainability reports was based on SDGs Ambition Benchmarks, GRI standard, ISO 26.000, the work of Haffar and Searcy (2018) that uses planetary boundaries to evaluate sustainability reports, EU Commission guidelines on sustainable reporting, and Carbon Disclosure Project guidelines for reporting greenhouse gas emissions.

The framework is divided into four main steps that are illustrated in Figure 1. First, mandatory information that all sustainability reports must include will be considered. The second step evaluates the scope of the report and its comprehensiveness by considering if the report is approaching the relevant themes for sustainability. We have individuated

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fifteen themes that will be detailed in the sequence. After identifying the themes that the report approaches, each one will be evaluated regarding its ambition and quality with the assistance of reference sheets. The ambition will be assessed by judging whether the goals adopted are relevant according to available science and impact-oriented. The quality will consider the actual information reported, especially the metrics accuracy, balance, clarity, and comparability evaluated.

2.1. Mandatory information

List of mandatory information regarding organisational profile and strategy from GRI guidelines.

Item	Yes	No
Name of the organization		
Activities, brands, products, and services		
Location of headquarters		
Location of operations		
Ownership and legal form		
Market served		
Scale of the organizations (number of employees, operations, net sales...)		
Supply chain (activities, primary brands, products, and services)		
External activities		

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Membership of associations		
Statement from senior decision-maker		
Evaluation of key impacts, risks and opportunities		
Values, principles, standards, and norms of behavior		
Mechanisms for advice and concerns about ethics		
Governance structure is detailed and transparent		
Delegating authority		

2.2. Scope, ambition, and quality

Macro-area	Theme	Source
Social	1. Diversity and equal opportunities	GRI, SDGs
	2. Fair compensation policy for employees	GRI, SDGs
	3. Work conditions	EU directive
	4. Consumer protection	ISO 26000, GRI
	5. Community involvement and development	ISO 26000, GRI
Environmental	6. Impact in water basins	GRI, SDGs
	7. Waste management	GRI, SDGs
	8. Management and use of hazardous pollutants and chemicals	SDGs, PB
	9. Sustainability of material inputs	SDGs, PB
	10. Energy Efficiency	GRI
	11. Greenhouse gas emissions	SDGs, CDP, PB
	12. Resource recovery	SDGs, PB
	13. Land degradation and deforestation	SDGs, PB
Governance	14. Anti-corruption and bribery	EU directive, SDGs, GRI
	15. Tax governance	GRI

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2.3. Score calculation

The evaluation of each theme could reach a maximum of 3 points and considered:

1. The inclusion of the theme with qualitative and quantitative information (1 point).
2. The presence of future goals and its ambition (1 point): the ambition of the goals was assessed by judging whether they were relevant according to available science and impact-oriented. Goals from different reports on the same theme were also compared.
3. The existence of metrics and their quality (1 point): the quality of the metrics was determined by evaluating their accuracy, balance, clarity, and comparability.

The final score of the report was determined by the sum of the fifteen themes scores and the score obtained in the evaluation of mandatory information (maximum score 1). As such, each report could reach a maximum of 46 points (maximum of 3 points for each one of the 15 themes + 1 point for mandatory information).

The following section provides a template for each of the 15 themes proposed, with examples regarding scope, ambition, and metrics quality.

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3. Template for each theme

1 - Diversity and equal opportunities		
This theme refers to the existence of inclusive workplaces where diversity of gender and age, and minorities are present at all levels of leadership and treated equally.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company's report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious?	Very ambitious	
Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eliminate gender pay gap. • Increase headcount gender/age diversity by level and function. • Increase recruitment balance between gender and age 	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization's performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salary and bonuses by level by gender/age. • Promotions by level by gender/age. • Employee turnover by category. • Applications by level by gender/age. • New recruits by level by gender. • New recruits from minorities. • Number of persons with disabilities employed. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization's performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
	Yes	

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Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	No	
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2 - Fair compensation policy for employees		
Companies' employees should receive a living wage that allows them to meet the minimum living standards according to the local costs of living.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company's report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% of employees are paid a living wage. • All suppliers and contractors adopt living wage policies. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization's performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of employees below a living wage by location and across the entire company. • Percentage differential between lowest wage and the living wage. • Adoption of sustainable procurement practices by department. • Number of contractors engaged on living wage policies. • Number of suppliers engaged on living wage policies. • Difference between highest and lowest pay. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization's performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous	Yes	
	No	

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years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).		
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3 - Work conditions		
Healthy and safe work conditions are recognized as a human right and are a requirement for any organization. Work conditions should prevent harm to the physical and mental health of workers and strive to promote it. Under no circumstances operations or suppliers should rely on children, forced, or compulsory labour.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company's report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All operations and suppliers comply with human rights. • All workers are engaged in the development of health and safety policies. • All workers have access to healthcare and wellness services. • Zero occupational accidents. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization's performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of occupational accidents. • Employees with injuries or occupational diseases. • Percentage of employees working under temporary contracts. • Number of operations and suppliers at significant risk of human rights violations. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization's performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous	Yes	
	No	

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years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).		
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4 – Consumer protection and satisfaction		
Businesses should ensure that their products are non-hazardous and do not cause harm to the health and safety of consumers. Adequate information should be provided to consumers to allow them to make informed choices. Any information collected by companies should also comply with data privacy standards.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company’s report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All products and services have their health and safety impacts assessed. • All products and services disclose information on health and safety impacts. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization’s performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidents of products or services non-compliance with regulations resulting in a fine or penalty. • Incidents of non-compliance with regulations resulting in a warning. • Incidents of non-compliance with voluntary codes. • Percentage of products and services that have health and safety impact assessed for improvement. • Customer retention rate. • Incidents of customers data breach. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization’s performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
	Yes	

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Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	No	
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5 – Community involvement and development		
Organisations can impact positively or negatively local communities. Companies are expected to avoid negative impacts and promote community development. To do so, companies need to identify and engage local stakeholders to understand their expectations and needs.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company’s report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All members of the local community are included in consultation committees and processes. • All projects have their impacts in local communities assessed. • Increase local community development programs based on local communities’ needs. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization’s performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage of operations with implemented local community engagement, impact assessments, and/or development programs. • Percentage of local groups and stakeholders engaged with the organization. • Share of jobs in the local community related to the organization. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization’s performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization’s performance over time (e.g. results from previous	Yes	
	No	

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years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).		
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6 - Impact in water basins and oceans		
The reports should address how companies manage its impacts in oceans and freshwater basins seeking to maintain the current availability of water, conducting adequate treatment of its wastewater, and not impairing the accessibility of local communities to water resources and aquatic ecosystems.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company's report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce the amount of water required for business activities, increasing reuse, recycling, and efficiency. • Phase out harmful chemicals in products and production. • Zero impact on local water quality and quantity. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization's performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water use by source (freshwater vs. other). • Water use in stressed regions / suppliers in stressed regions. • Water recycling rate. • Total water discharge. • Total discharge outside legal thresholds. • Level of water treatment. • Local population with access to clean water. • Employees with access to safe water. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization's performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	

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Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	Yes	
	No	

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7 – Waste management		
The report should expose what practices organisations adopt to evaluate and optimise their material flows, seeking to eliminate all solid waste from their operations.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company’s report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious?	Very ambitious	
<p>Examples of ambitious goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zero waste to landfill or incineration. • Reduce waste generation at the source. • Increase the selling of recycled waste and by-products to other markets and sectors. • Increase the re-use of operational waste and by-products to its own operation and increasing circularity. 	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
<p>Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization’s performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregated volume of each waste stream. • Amount of hazardous waste generated. • Sites designated as zero waste to landfill or incineration. • Total waste by re-use or recycling. • New products through by-product innovation. • Revenue generated with waste re-use, recycling, or by-product innovation. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
<p>Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization’s performance.</p>	Yes	
	No	
<p>Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.</p>	Yes	
	No	

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Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	Yes	
	No	

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8 - Management and use of hazardous pollutants and chemicals		
Sustainability reports should contain information regarding the hazardous pollutants and chemicals companies use in their production processes and manage them. This theme includes pollutants released into the air (such as soot or particulate matter), water (such as groundwater contaminated with waste or fertilizer) and soil (such as hazardous mining byproducts).		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company's report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zero discharge of hazardous pollutants and chemicals in the environment. • Phase out of high-risk and/or high-volume pollutants. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization's performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volume and risk factor of chemical products by category. • Hazardous products/services with established phase-out plans. • Total discharge of hazardous chemicals by location type. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization's performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	Yes	
	No	

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9 - Sustainability of material inputs		
Companies should embed circular economy practices into material selection and product design. Sustainability reports should illustrate what practices the company adopt to increase the sustainability of products and packages feedstocks.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company's report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% sustainable material inputs that are renewable, recyclable, or reusable. • Increase in products which have achieved 100% sustainable or circular inputs. • Increase in sustainable material inputs by spend and volume. • Increase total products with an end-of-life solution. • All suppliers follow the same environmental, social, and governance criteria adopted by the company. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization's performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantity of materials that are used to produce and package products and services by renewable and non-renewable sources. • Total renewable materials by product. • Percentage of reclaimed products and their packaging materials for each product category. 	Yes	
	No	

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of recycled input materials used to manufacture the organization's primary products and services. 		
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization's performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	Yes	
	No	

10 – Energy Efficiency		
Reports should contain information on the company energy usage and strategies to reducing it. The more efficient use of energy and the adoption of renewable energy sources is essential for combating climate change and lowering an organization’s overall environmental footprint.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company’s report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% of energy sourced from renewable sources. • Reduce the energy intensity of operation processes and products. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization’s performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total energy consumption from non-renewable sources versus renewable sources. • Organization’s energy intensity ratio. • Total reductions in energy consumption achieved. • Increments in energy efficiency of sold products and services. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization’s performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization’s performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	Yes	
	No	

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11 – Greenhouse gas emissions		
Mitigating greenhouse gas emissions is essential for business. Sustainability reports should convey goals and strategies to ensure the achievement of net-zero emissions by 2050, a goal in line with international and European climate policy and the best available science.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company’s report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Net-zero carbon emissions by 2050. • Reduction in scope 1 emissions (direct carbon emissions from sources that are controlled or owned by the organization) • Reduction in scope 2 emissions (indirect emissions associated with energy use) • Reduction in scope 3 emissions (non-direct carbon emissions derived from product transportation and use and treatment at end of life) • Increase in GHG removal. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization’s performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total emissions from the company productive process. • Total Scope 2 emissions (market-based & location-based emissions). • Estimated upstream & downstream emissions. • Total GHG removal by removal technology. • Annual carbon emissions vs. annual removals. • Total carbon credits purchased by the company and its source. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		

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Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization's performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	Yes	
	No	

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12 – Resource Recovery		
This theme approaches the responsibility that companies have for their products after their use. Companies should strive to adopt circular practices that ensure that products are recycled, recovered, or reused. Reverse logistics or product as-a-service practices are examples of how companies can perform resource recovery.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company’s report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All products contain renewable and recyclable inputs. • Increase in revenue from circular models. • Increase in product collection and recycling. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization’s performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total renewable materials by product. • Product recovery per business model. • Product lifecycle by product type. • Total material collected and recycled. • Collection sites and programs by type. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization’s performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization’s performance over time (e.g. results from previous	Yes	
	No	

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years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).		
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13 - Land degradation and deforestation		
Businesses should maintain or enhance the quality of the natural environment in which they operate. Businesses should not impact the amount and quality of land resources necessary for an ecosystem to function. A limited impact in forests is also necessary by ensuring reforestation and regeneration.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company's report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious?	Very ambitious	
Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease in land used or affected. • Increase of soil health. • Increase of land restored vs. degraded. • All suppliers comply with local forest protection regulations. 	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization's performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hectares of land managed. • Rate of deforestation in protected areas. • Per cent suppliers employing land management. • Size/location of habitats restored. • Proportion of disturbed to restored land. • Percentage of suppliers with no gross deforestation in the reporting year. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization's performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous	Yes	
	No	

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years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).		
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14 - Anti-corruption and bribery		
Organizations need to work towards eliminating and preventing cases of corruption and bribery. In the short term, all companies should present targets to eradicate such incidents inside their operations. However, companies should also be concerned with bribery across their value chain and work towards its eradication. Italian companies must also comply with the Law 231/2001 by ensuring a periodically revised evaluation of corruption risks.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company's report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious?	Very ambitious	
Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in confirmed bribery incidents. • 100% of employees & business partners trained in the topic. • Develop of policies to reduce bribery risks. • Establish mechanism to encourage and protect whistleblowers. • Ensure the revision and updating of the 231 module. 	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
	Goals identified in the report:	
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization's performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total operations assessed for risk. • Total risks identified and mitigated. • Number of stakeholders trained in anti-bribery subdivided by group (e.g. board; employee level; business partner). • Incidents by outcome (e.g. dismissal;) and by responsible party (supplier, employee). 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization's performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
	Yes	

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Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization's performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	No	
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15 – Tax governance		
Organizations must comply with tax regulations in all countries in which they operate. The avoidance of taxes can impair public investments, resulting in a negative impact on society. Companies are expected to be transparent when reporting taxes, clearly indicating taxes paid in each country of operation.		
Scope: Is the theme approached in the company’s report?	Yes	
	No	
Is the theme reported in a balanced way (e.g. reporting strengths and aspects where the company can improve)?	Yes	
	No	
Ambition: Are the goals adopted ambitious? Examples of ambitious goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure effective cooperation with tax authorities. 	Very ambitious	
	Somewhat ambitious	
	Neutral	
	Not very ambitious	
	Not at all ambitious	
Goals identified in the report:		
Metrics quality:		
Accuracy: The reported information is sufficiently accurate and detailed for stakeholders to assess the reporting organization’s performance. Example of fundamental metrics to accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tax paid vs number of workers for each country of operation. Total tax incentives received by the company. 	Yes	
	No	
Metrics identified in the report:		
Balance: the reported information reflects positive and negative aspects of the reporting organization’s performance.	Yes	
	No	
Clarity: the reported information is understandable and accessible to stakeholders.	Yes	
	No	
Comparability: The reported information enables stakeholders to analyze changes in the organization’s performance over time (e.g. results from previous years are included, and/or the company performance is compared with sectoral benchmarks).	Yes	
	No	

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References

United Nations Global Compact (2021), **SDG Ambition Guide: Setting Goals for the Decade of Action**. Viewed 20 October 2021 <<https://unglobalcompact.org/take-action/sdg-ambition>>

Global Reporting Initiative (2021), **Sustainability Reporting Standards**. Viewed 20 October 2021 <<https://www.globalreporting.org/how-to-use-the-gri-standards/gri-standards-english-language/>>

ISO (2010), **ISO 26.000 – Guidance on social responsibility**. Viewed 20 October 2021 <<https://www.iso.org/standard/42546.html>>

Haffar, M., & Searcy, C. (2018). **Target-setting for ecological resilience: Are companies setting environmental sustainability targets in line with planetary thresholds?**. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 27(7), 1079-1092.

Council Directive 2014/95/EU amending Directive 2013/34/EU as regards disclosure of non-financial and diversity information by certain large undertakings and groups Text with EEA relevance, 2014. Viewed 20 October 2021 <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014L0095>>

Carbon Disclosure Project (2021), **Guidelines for companies disclosure**. Viewed 20 October 2021 <<https://www.cdp.net/en/guidance/guidance-for-companies>>